

PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING AND ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY DETERMINATION OF BOERHAAVIA DIFFUSA ROOTS HYDRO ALCOHOLIC EXTRACT

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Article Received on 28 April 2026,
Article Revised on 18 May 2026,
Article Published on 01 June 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20443599>

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How To Cite This Article: Dr. Fathima Nausheen Usman^{1*}, Dr. Atthapu Thirupathaiah², Dr. Madireddy Mamata³. (2026). Phytochemical Screening and Anthelmintic Activity Determination of Boerhaavia Diffusa Roots Hydro Alcoholic Extract. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(6), 781–787.

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ABSTRACT

Boerhaavia diffusa roots are widely used in traditional medicine for the treatment of various disorders. The present study was carried out to evaluate the phytochemical constituents and anthelmintic activity of the hydroalcoholic extract of *B. diffusa* roots. Anthelmintic activity was assessed using *Pheretima posthuma* as the experimental worm model. Different concentrations of the extract (25, 50, and 100 mg/ml) were tested and compared with albendazole as the standard drug. The activity was evaluated by recording the paralysis and death times of worms. The results revealed significant dose-dependent anthelmintic activity, where higher concentrations produced faster paralysis and death. The presence of phenolic tannin, and flavonoid constituents may contribute to the observed activity. The study concludes that the hydroalcoholic extract of *B. diffusa* roots possesses promising anthelmintic

potential and may be useful for further herbal drug development.

KEYWORDS: *Boerhaavia diffusa*, *Pheretima posthuma*, anthelmintic activity, albendazole.

INTRODUCTION

Plants are vital to human survival and have been used as sources of medicine since ancient times. Nature's pharmacy provides numerous remedies for the treatment of human ailments.^[1] India possesses a rich heritage of traditional herbal medicine with extensive well-documented knowledge regarding the therapeutic uses of medicinal plants.^[2] Herbal medicines are widely utilized by traditional practitioners throughout the world for the management and treatment of various diseases.^[3] In recent years, the development of synthetic drugs has increased remarkably; however, many synthetic medicines are associated with undesirable side effects and toxicities. In contrast, medicinal plants continue to occupy a significant position in healthcare because of their effectiveness, safety, affordability, and minimal adverse effects.^[4] Medicinal plants contain a variety of bioactive constituents such as alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolics, tannins, and glycosides that are responsible for their therapeutic activities. Among these medicinal plants, *Boerhaavia diffusa* is an important herb traditionally used for the treatment of several disorders including inflammation, liver diseases, urinary disorders, and parasitic infections. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to evaluate the phytochemical constituents and anthelmintic activity of the hydroalcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa* roots.

B. diffusa is an important medicinal plant widely used in traditional Ayurvedic medicine for the treatment of various diseases. The plant is commonly known as Punarnava and belongs to the family Nyctaginaceae. It possesses several pharmacological activities such as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, hepatoprotective, antimicrobial, and anthelmintic properties. The roots of *B. diffusa* contain bioactive constituents including alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, phenolic compounds, and tannins. These phytoconstituents are responsible for its therapeutic potential. Herbal medicines derived from this plant are considered safer and economical compared to synthetic drugs. The increasing resistance and side effects associated with synthetic anthelmintic drugs have created interest in medicinal plants as alternative therapies. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to evaluate the phytochemical constituents and anthelmintic activity of the hydroalcoholic extract of *B. diffusa* roots. The study aims to scientifically validate its traditional medicinal use.

Globally, parasitic worm infections affect around 2 billion individuals. Anthelmintics are drugs that either kill or immobilize parasitic worms, enabling the body to expel them. There are other terrible names for them: vermifuges and vermicides. Unfortunately, gastrointestinal

helminths are not treatable by the current helminth drugs. These days, using certain synthetic anthelmintics can be hazardous to people. It is safe to utilize anthelmintic plants, such as *Centratherum anthelminticum*, *Ocimum sanctum*, and *Carica papaya* etc.

Figure 1: *Boerhaavia diffusa*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and authentication

Boerhaavia diffusa roots were gathered from the surroundings of Nalgonda, Telangana State, India. Botanist Dr. K. Srinivasa Reddy, Assistant Professor, Department of Botany, Govt. Degree College for Women, Nalgonda, Telangana, authenticated the authenticity of the plant specimen. After being shade-dried, the plant material was pulverized and stored in an airtight container. The material that had been pulverized was used in the extraction process.

Extract preparation

Boerhaavia diffusa roots powder was extracted using macerating 90 grams of the powdered sample in 900 mL of hydroalcoholic solvent for 72 hours at room temperature. After extraction, the extract is concentrated and removed from plant debris with a four-fold muslin cloth. It was determined that the color, consistency, and yield % were. The extracted product was used to measure anthelmintic activity, and phytochemical screening.^[5]

Phytochemical screening

Using standardized procedures, the extract was subjected to phytochemical screening to determine the content of tannins, phenols, flavonoids, glycosides, and alkaloids etc.^[6]

Biological study

Because *Pheretima postuma* bears morphological and physiological similarities to human intestinal roundworm parasites, healthy adult Indian earthworms were employed in this work. Every earthworm had roughly the same size. They were gathered from a nearby location, cleaned, and stored in water.

Drugs

Each group tested different dosages of *Boerhaavia diffusa* roots hydroalcoholic extract. The control was the normal saline solution. The standard medication was albendazole.

Experimental method

Using adult *Pheretima postuma* Indian earthworms, anthelmintic activity was evaluated. By using bioassay, different concentrations of each extract and drug (25, 50, and 100 mg/ml) were evaluated to determine the worms' paralysis and death times. As a standard, albendazole was utilized, while saline water served as the control. The earthworms were taken out of the damp soil, cleaned with normal saline to get rid of all the feces, and then utilized for the study of anthelmintic. The earthworms were divided up into three groups, with each group having six earthworms. Before experiments started, all of the extract and the standard drug solution were prepared from fresh in normal saline. Standard drug solutions and extract were placed in different Petri dishes. The earthworms were all discharged into the 20 ml formulation in the following manner: Three different concentrations of hydroalcoholic extract and albendazole.

The amount of time it took for each worm to become paralyzed and die was noted. When there was no movement at all, with the exception of the worms shaking violently, it was noted that the time for paralysis had arrived. After being submerged in heated water (50⁰C), the worms lost their ability to move and their body colors faded, signaling their death.^[7]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The powdered roots of *Boerhaavia diffusa* were extracted using a maceration process and a hydroalcoholic solvent. Table 1 contains information on colour, consistency, and yield percentage.

Table 1: Yield and physical appearance of hydroalcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa* roots.

S. No	Property	Report
1	Colour	Dark brown to reddish brown
2	Odour	Characteristic
3	Consistency	Sticky, semisolid
4	% Yield	14%

Table 2's tannins, phenols, flavonoids, glycosides, and alkaloids have been detected during preliminary phytochemical screening.

Table 2: Preliminary phytochemical screening of hydroalcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa* roots.

S. No	Constituents	Report
1	Carbohydrates	Present
2	Tannins & phenols	Present
3	Proteins	Present
4	Alkaloids	Absent
5	Glycosides	Present
6	Flavonoids	Present
7	Saponins	Present
8	Amino acids	Present
9	Steroids	Absent

Numerous studies in the past have suggested that one of the key elements for the antioxidant activity of medicinal plants is phenolic compounds. Another group of physiologically active substances that have long been used to treat a variety of illnesses in humans, including cardiovascular disease, are flavonoids. Tannins have been linked to several health-promoting properties, including antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-mutagenic properties.^[8] Thus, our study clearly shows that the high concentration of phenol and flavonoids is responsible for some of the medical benefits of plant roots.

Boerhaavia diffusa roots hydro alcoholic extract showed dose-dependent anthelmintic action Table 3 displays that the standard medicine Albendazole exhibits paralysis at 19 minutes and death at 28 minutes, while the hydroalcoholic extract exhibits paralysis at 29 minutes and death at 40 minutes. Tannins were found to have anthelmintic action based on phytochemical screening. Tannins are polyphenolic substances chemically. When tannins attach to free proteins in the host animal's gastrointestinal tract or to glycoprotein on the parasite's cuticle, they can be fatal. The necessity to isolate the active ingredients that cause activity will be a future focus.

Table 3: Anthelmintic activity of hydro alcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa* roots.

S.No	Groups	Conc.(mg/ml)	Response	
			Paralysis time (min)	Deathtime (min)
1	Normal control	-----	-----	-----
2	Hydro alcoholic	25	76	89
		50	43	62
		100	29	40
3	Albendazole	25	47	58
		50	29	36
		100	19	28

All values represent Mean +SD; n= 6 in each group.

CONCLUSION

The present study concludes that the hydroalcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa* roots possesses significant anthelmintic activity against *Pheretima posthuma*. The extract showed dose-dependent activity by reducing the paralysis and death time of worms when compared with the control group. The observed activity may be attributed to the presence of phytochemical constituents such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, phenolic compounds, and saponins present in the extract. Among the tested concentrations, the higher concentration exhibited better anthelmintic effect and showed results comparable to the standard drug albendazole.

The study scientifically supports the traditional use of *Boerhaavia diffusa* roots in the treatment of helminthic infections. Further studies are required to isolate the active constituents and evaluate their mechanism of action and safety profile for the development of effective herbal anthelmintic agents.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I express my sincere gratitude to our Principal and Management for providing the necessary facilities and support to carry out this work successfully. I also extend my thanks to all the faculty members of the Department of Pharmacy for their suggestions and cooperation during this work. I am grateful to the laboratory staff for providing the required chemicals, instruments, and technical assistance. I would also like to thank my friends and classmates for their help and encouragement during the completion of this project. Finally, I express my heartfelt gratitude to my parents and family members for their constant support, motivation, and blessings throughout my academic work.

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